

Fuzzy Inference Engine Specification for PID Auto-Tuning Control

Supplementary Material to: "Deterministic Compliance Failures in Large Language Models: A Structural Analysis Using a Legacy Fuzzy Inference Benchmark"

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Fuzzy Inference System Evolution and Logical Validation Scheme

1. 1987 Legacy Reproduction Path

2. Current Experiment: LLM Logical Validation

Preparation for Logical Validation Scheme

1. Input system parameters (L, Tl, τ) to the reproduced system.
2. The system automatically calculates initial PID via Takahashi-Chan's method.
3. Execute auto-tuning to derive final correction values ($\Delta Kp, \Delta Ki, \Delta Kd$).
4. Use ($\alpha 1 - \alpha 5$) and ($\Delta Kp, i, d$) as ground truth for LLM logical validation.
5. Logic is human-traceable via inference flowchart and fuzzy set tables

Calculations are fully deterministic and human-traceable

Fuzzy Inference Logic Flowchart

Inference I (1/3)

TableB-1-1. Universe of Discourse α_4

Element	Range of Real values
0	$0 \leq \alpha_4 < 100$
1	$100 \leq \alpha_4 < 300$
2	$300 \leq \alpha_4 < 500$
3	$500 \leq \alpha_4 < 1000$
4	$1000 \leq \alpha_4 < 5000$
5	$5000 \leq \alpha_4 < 10000$
6	$10000 \leq \alpha_4 < 50000$
7	$50000 \leq \alpha_4$

TableB-1-2. Universe of Discourse α_5

Element	Range of Real values
0	$0 \leq \alpha_5 < 0.1$
1	$0.1 \leq \alpha_5 < 0.5$
2	$0.5 \leq \alpha_5 < 1$
3	$1 \leq \alpha_5 < 5$
4	$5 \leq \alpha_5 < 10$
5	$10 \leq \alpha_5$

Table B-1-3. Universe of Discourse for ΔK_d

Element	Range (V)	Output
0	0	0
1	$0 < \Delta K_d \leq 14$	7
2	$14 < \Delta K_d \leq 26$	20
3	$26 < \Delta K_d \leq 34$	30
4	$34 < \Delta K_d \leq 40$	37
5	$40 < \Delta K_d \leq 50$	45
6	$50 < \Delta K_d \leq 60$	55
7	$60 < \Delta K_d$	70

Inference I (2/3)

Table B-1-4: Membership Values for α_4

Label	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
EB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	1
VB	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.8	1	0.5
B	0	0	0.2	0.8	1	0.8	0.2	0
M	0	0.2	1	0.8	0.2	0	0	0

Table B-1-5: Membership Values for α_5

Label	0	1	2	3	4	5
B	0	0	0.2	0.9	1	1

Table B-1-6: Membership Values for ΔK_d

Label	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
EB	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.5	1.0
VB	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.8	1.0	0.5
B	0	0	0.2	0.7	1.0	0.7	0.2	0
M	0	0.5	1.0	0.8	0.2	0	0	0

Inference I (3/3)

Inference I: Rule Matrix ($\alpha_4, \alpha_5 \rightarrow \Delta Kd$)

α_4 / α_5	B (Big)
EB	ΔKd is EB
VB	ΔKd is VB
B	ΔKd is B
M	ΔKd is M

✂ Adjustment Rules:

IF α_4 is [Label]
AND α_5 is B
THEN ΔKd is [Result]

1. Fuzzification

Convert input real values into "Elements" based on the Universe of Discourse.

- α_4 : Select Element 0–7 based on its real value range.
- α_5 : Select Element 0–5 based on its real value range.

2. Membership Grade Extraction & Confidence Filter

Identify the membership grade (μ) for the selected Elements.

- Exit Condition**: If the membership grade μ of the selected input is **less than 0.8**, set $\Delta Kd = 0$ and **Exit** the process immediately and go to the Inference II.
- Multiple Labels**: If an input Element corresponds to multiple labels (e.g., both **VB** and **B** have $\mu \geq 0.8$):
 1. Execute the Adjustment Rules for each label individually.
 2. Identify the resulting ΔKd label elements.
 3. Select the final output ΔKd Element by calculating the **average of these elements**.
 4. Round up any decimal results to the nearest whole number.

3. Adjustment Rules (Rule Base)

Apply the following linguistic rules to determine the output label.

- Rule 1**: IF α_4 is EB and α_5 is B THEN $\Delta Kd=EB$
- Rule 2**: ELSE IF α_4 is VB and α_5 is B THEN $\Delta Kd=VB$
- Rule 3**: ELSE IF α_4 is B and α_5 is B THEN $\Delta Kd=B$
- Rule 4**: ELSE IF α_4 is M and α_5 is B THEN $\Delta Kd=M$

4. Defuzzification & Output Selection

Determine the final real output value from Table B-1-6.

- Exit Condition**: If the membership grade μ of the selected output is **less than 0.8**, set $\Delta Kd = 0$ and **Exit** the process immediately and go to the Inference II.
- Mean of Maxima (MoM)**: If multiple output Elements share the same maximum membership value, use the **Mean of Maxima** method to select the final output Element.
- Final Conversion**: Map the selected Element to the "Output Value" (0–70) as defined in Table B-1-3.

Inference II (1/3)

Table B-2-1: Universe of Discourse for α_3

Element	Range of Real Values (α_3)
0	$0 \leq \alpha_3 < 100$
1	$100 \leq \alpha_3 < 200$
2	$200 \leq \alpha_3 < 400$
3	$400 \leq \alpha_3 < 600$
4	$600 \leq \alpha_3 < 1000$
5	$1000 \leq \alpha_3 < 10000$
6	$10000 \leq \alpha_3$

Table B-2-2: Universe of Discourse for ΔKd (Inference II)

Element	Range of Real Values (ΔKd)	Output
0	0	0
1	$0 \leq \Delta Kd < 8$	4
2	$8 \leq \Delta Kd < 12$	10
3	$12 \leq \Delta Kd < 18$	15
4	$18 \leq \Delta Kd < 22$	20
5	$22 \leq \Delta Kd < 28$	25
6	$28 \leq \Delta Kd < 32$	30
7	$32 \leq \Delta Kd < 68$	50
8	$68 \leq \Delta Kd$	80

Inference II (2/3)

Table B-2-3: Membership Values for α_3

Label / Element	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
VB	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.8	1.0
B	0	0.1	0.5	0.7	1.0	0.8	0.2
RB	0	0.2	0.8	1.0	0.8	0.2	0
SB	0.2	0.7	1.0	0.8	0.2	0	0

Table B-2-4: Membership Values for ΔK_d (Inference II)

Label / Element	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
VB	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.8	1	0.7	0.2
B	0	0	0.2	0.7	1	0.8	0.2	0	0
RB	0	0.2	0.8	1	0.8	0.2	0	0	0
SB	0.2	0.7	1	0.8	0.2	0	0	0	0

Inference II (3/3)

Inference II : Rule Matrix ($\alpha_3 \rightarrow \Delta Kd$)

α_3	ΔKd
VB	VB
B	B
RB	RB
SB	SB

✂ Adjustment Rules:
 IF α_3 is [Label]
 THEN ΔKd is [Result]

1. Fuzzification

Convert input real values into "Elements" based on the Universe of Discourse.

• α_3 : Select Element 0–6 based on its real value range.

2. Membership Grade Extraction & Confidence Filter

Identify the membership grade (μ) for the selected Elements.

•**Exit Condition**: If the membership grade μ of the selected input is **less than 0.8**, set $\Delta Kd = 0$ and **Exit** the process immediately and go to the condition $\alpha_2 \geq \alpha_1$.

•**Multiple Labels**: If an input Element corresponds to multiple labels (e.g., both **VB** and **B** have $\mu \geq 0.8$):

1. Execute the Adjustment Rules for each label individually.
2. Identify the resulting ΔKd label elements.
3. Select the final output ΔKd Element by calculating the **average of these elements**.
4. Round up any decimal results to the nearest whole number.

3. Adjustment Rules (Rule Base)

Apply the following linguistic rules to determine the output label.

•**Rule 1**: IF α_3 is VB THEN $\Delta Kd=VB$

•**Rule 2**: ELSE IF α_3 is B THEN $\Delta Kd=B$

•**Rule 3**: ELSE IF α_3 is RB THEN $\Delta Kd=RB$

•**Rule 4**: ELSE IF α_3 is SB THEN $\Delta Kd=SB$

4. Defuzzification & Output Selection

Determine the final real output value from Table B-2-4.

•**Exit Condition**: If the membership grade μ of the selected output is **less than 0.8**, set $\Delta Kd = 0$ and **Exit** the process immediately and go to the condition $\alpha_2 \geq \alpha_1$.

•**Mean of Maxima (MoM)**: If multiple output Elements share the same maximum membership value, use the **Mean of Maxima** method to select the final output Element.

•**Final Conversion**: Map the selected Element to the "Output Value" (0–80) as defined in Table B-2-2.

Conditional Branching: If the **inferred** value ΔKd is greater than 0, the inference engine must terminate the current tuning cycle immediately. In this case, do not proceed to Inference III or Inference IV. This ensures that derivative compensation is applied first to suppress oscillation before adjusting proportional or integral gains.

Inference III(1/4)

Table B-3-1. Complete Universe of Discourse for α_2

Element	Range (%)	Element	Range (%)
0	$0 \leq \alpha < 2$	13	$8 \leq \alpha < 8.5$
1	$2 \leq \alpha < 2.5$	14	$8.5 \leq \alpha < 9$
2	$2.5 \leq \alpha < 3$	15	$9 \leq \alpha < 9.5$
3	$3 \leq \alpha < 3.5$	16	$9.5 \leq \alpha < 10$
4	$3.5 \leq \alpha < 4$	17	$10 \leq \alpha < 12$
5	$4 \leq \alpha < 4.5$	18	$12 \leq \alpha < 15$
6	$4.5 \leq \alpha < 5$	19	$15 \leq \alpha < 18$
7	$5 \leq \alpha < 5.5$	20	$18 \leq \alpha < 20$
8	$5.5 \leq \alpha < 6$	21	$20 \leq \alpha < 25$
9	$6 \leq \alpha < 6.5$	22	$25 \leq \alpha < 30$
10	$6.5 \leq \alpha < 7$	23	$30 \leq \alpha < 35$
11	$7 \leq \alpha < 7.5$	24	$35 \leq \alpha < 50$
12	$7.5 \leq \alpha < 8$	25	$50 \leq \alpha$

Table B-3-2. Universe of Discourse for ΔK_p

Idx	Range	Out	Idx	Range	Out
0	$0 \leq \Delta K < 2$	0	13	$8 \leq \Delta K < 8.5$	8
1	$2 \leq \Delta K < 2.5$	2	14	$8.5 \leq \Delta K < 9$	8.5
2	$2.5 \leq \Delta K < 3$	2.5	15	$9 \leq \Delta K < 9.5$	9
3	$3 \leq \Delta K < 3.5$	3	16	$9.5 \leq \Delta K < 10$	9.5
4	$3.5 \leq \Delta K < 4$	3.5	17	$10 \leq \Delta K < 11$	10
5	$4 \leq \Delta K < 4.5$	4	18	$11 \leq \Delta K < 13$	12
6	$4.5 \leq \Delta K < 5$	4.5	19	$13 \leq \Delta K < 17$	15
7	$5 \leq \Delta K < 5.5$	5	20	$17 \leq \Delta K < 19$	18
8	$5.5 \leq \Delta K < 6$	5.5	21	$19 \leq \Delta K < 21$	20
9	$6 \leq \Delta K < 6.5$	6	22	$21 \leq \Delta K < 29$	25
10	$6.5 \leq \Delta K < 7$	6.5	23	$29 \leq \Delta K < 31$	30
11	$7 \leq \Delta K < 7.5$	7	24	$31 \leq \Delta K$	35
12	$7.5 \leq \Delta K < 8$	7.5			

Inference III (2/4)

Table B-3-3: Membership Values for α_2

Element/ Label	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25
EB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.9	1	1	1
VB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.7	0.9	1	0.9	0.7	0.2	0
B	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.7	0.9	1	0.9	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0
SB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.5	0.7	0.9	1	0.9	0.7	0.2	0	0	0	0	0
RAM	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	0.9	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
M	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	0.9	0.7	0.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
RBM	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	0.9	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SS	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.9	1	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
VS	0	0.5	0.7	0.8	1	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ES	0.7	1	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Inference III (3/4)

Table B-3-4: Membership Values for ΔK_p

Element/ Label	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	
EB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.7	0.9	1
VB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	1	0.9	0.7	
B	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.9	1	0.9	0.7	0.2	0	
SB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.9	1	0.9	0.7	0.2	0	0	0	
RAM	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	0.9	0.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	
M	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.8	0.9	1	0.9	0.9	0.7	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
RBM	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.8	0.9	1	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
SS	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.8	1	0.9	0.9	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
S	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.9	0.9	1	0.9	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
VS	0	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
ES	0.5	0.8	1	0.9	0.9	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Inference III (4/4)

Fuzzification

Convert the input real values into "Elements" based on the Universe of Discourse (Table B-3-1).

•**α2**: Select Element **0–25** based on its real value range.

Inference III: Rule Matrix (α2 → ΔKp)

α2 (Input)	ΔKp (Output)
EB	EB
VB	VB
B	B
SB	SB
RAM	RAM
M	M
RBM	RBM
SS	SS
S	S
VS	VS
ES	ES

※ Adjustment Rules:

IF α2 is [Label] THEN ΔKp is [Result]

2. Membership Grade Extraction & Safety Exit

Identify the membership grade (μ) for the selected Element using Table B-3-3.

•**CRITICAL EXIT**: If the membership grade μ of the selected input is **LESS THAN 0.7**:

•Set **ΔKp = 0**.

•**TERMINATE** the entire inference loop immediately. No further processes or inferences are executed.

•**PROCEED**: If the membership grade μ is **0.7 or higher**, proceed to the Adjustment Rules.

•Crucial Rule for Output Determination (Aggregation & Defuzzification):

If multiple α2 labels (e.g., "B" and "VB") share the same maximum membership grade, the system must not pick only one. Instead, you must follow these exact steps: (1) Independent Evaluation: Identify the target Element Number of ΔKp for each applicable label independently based on the rules. (2) Mean of Indices with Roundup: Calculate the arithmetic mean of all identified Element Numbers. If the result has a decimal, you must round it up (ceil) to the next integer. (3) retrieve the final gain value ΔKp from Table B-3-2 using this unified Element Number. (4) **TERMINATE** the entire inference loop immediately. No further processes or inferences are executed.

No further processes or inferences are executed

For instance, If Label "B" points to Element 16 and Label "VB" points to Element 20: Calculation: $(16 + 20) / 2 = 18$: The value at Element 18 (which is ΔKp=15), not Element 16 or 20. Note that "B" and "VB" share the same maximum membership grade in this case.

3. Adjustment Rules (Complete Rule Base)

Apply the following linguistic rules to determine the output label. In Inference III, α2 labels map directly to ΔKp labels.

•**Rule 1**: IF α2 is **EB** THEN ΔKp = **EB**

•**Rule 2**: ELSE IF α2 is **VB** THEN ΔKp = **VB**

•**Rule 3**: ELSE IF α2 is **B** THEN ΔKp = **B**

•**Rule 4**: ELSE IF α2 is **SB** THEN ΔKp = **SB**

•**Rule 5**: ELSE IF α2 is **RAM** THEN ΔKp = **RAM**

•**Rule 6**: ELSE IF α2 is **M** THEN ΔKp = **M**

•**Rule 7**: ELSE IF α2 is **RBM** THEN ΔKp = **RBM**

•**Rule 8**: ELSE IF α2 is **SS** THEN ΔKp = **SS**

•**Rule 9**: ELSE IF α2 is **S** THEN ΔKp = **S**

•**Rule 10**: ELSE IF α2 is **VS** THEN ΔKp = **VS**

•**Rule 11**: ELSE IF α2 is **ES** THEN ΔKp = **ES**

4. Defuzzification & Loop Termination

4-1. Identify the resulting ΔKp Element based on the selected label and its membership grade from Table B-3-4.

4-2. **Mean of Maxima (MoM)**: If multiple output Elements share the same maximum membership value, use the **Mean of Maxima** method to select the final output Element.

4-3. **Final Conversion**: Map the selected Element to the "Output Value" (0–70) as defined in Table B-3-2.

4-4. **EXIT CONDITION**: If the membership grade μ of the selected output is **LESS THAN 0.7**, set **ΔKp = 0**.

4-5. **SYSTEM TERMINATION**: After completing these steps, the entire inference loop ends. There are no subsequent inference stages after Inference III.

Inference IV(1/4)

Table B-4-1. Complete Universe of Discourse for α_1

Element	Range (%)	Element	Range (%)
0	$0 \leq \alpha < 2$	13	$8 \leq \alpha < 8.5$
1	$2 \leq \alpha < 2.5$	14	$8.5 \leq \alpha < 9$
2	$2.5 \leq \alpha < 3$	15	$9 \leq \alpha < 9.5$
3	$3 \leq \alpha < 3.5$	16	$9.5 \leq \alpha < 10$
4	$3.5 \leq \alpha < 4$	17	$10 \leq \alpha < 12$
5	$4 \leq \alpha < 4.5$	18	$12 \leq \alpha < 15$
6	$3.5 \leq \alpha < 5$	19	$15 \leq \alpha < 18$
7	$5 \leq \alpha < 5.5$	20	$18 \leq \alpha < 20$
8	$5.5 \leq \alpha < 6$	21	$20 \leq \alpha < 25$
9	$6 \leq \alpha < 6.5$	22	$25 \leq \alpha < 30$
10	$6.5 \leq \alpha < 7$	23	$30 \leq \alpha < 35$
11	$7 \leq \alpha < 7.5$	24	$35 \leq \alpha < 50$
12	$7.5 \leq \alpha < 8$	25	$50 \leq \alpha$

Table B-4-2. Universe of Discourse for ΔK_i

Idx	Range	Out	Idx	Range	Out
0	$0 \leq \Delta K < 2$	0	13	$8 \leq \Delta K < 8.5$	8
1	$2 \leq \Delta K < 2.5$	2	14	$8.5 \leq \Delta K < 9$	8.5
2	$2.5 \leq \Delta K < 3$	2.5	15	$9 \leq \Delta K < 9.5$	9
3	$3 \leq \Delta K < 3.5$	3	16	$9.5 \leq \Delta K < 10$	9.5
4	$3.5 \leq \Delta K < 4$	3.5	17	$10 \leq \Delta K < 11$	10
5	$4 \leq \Delta K < 4.5$	4	18	$11 \leq \Delta K < 13$	12
6	$4.5 \leq \Delta K < 5$	4.5	19	$13 \leq \Delta K < 17$	15
7	$5 \leq \Delta K < 5.5$	5	20	$17 \leq \Delta K < 19$	18
8	$5.5 \leq \Delta K < 6$	5.5	21	$19 \leq \Delta K < 21$	20
9	$6 \leq \Delta K < 6.5$	6	22	$21 \leq \Delta K < 29$	25
10	$6.5 \leq \Delta K < 7$	6.5	23	$29 \leq \Delta K < 31$	30
11	$7 \leq \Delta K < 7.5$	7	24	$31 \leq \Delta K$	35
12	$7.5 \leq \Delta K < 8$	7.5			

Inference IV (2/4)

Table B-4-3: Membership Values for α_1

Element/ Label	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25
EB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.9	0.9	1	1
VB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.7	0.9	1	0.9	0.7	0.2	0
B	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.7	0.9	1	0.9	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0
SB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.5	0.7	0.9	1	0.9	0.7	0.2	0	0	0	0	0
RAM	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	0.9	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
M	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
RBM	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
SS	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.9	1	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S	0	0.2	0.5	0.8	0.9	0.9	1	0.9	0.9	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
VS	0.2	0.7	0.9	1	0.9	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ES	0.7	1	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Inference IV (3/4)

Table B-4-4: Membership Values for ΔKi

Element/ Label	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	
EB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.9	0.9
VB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.7	0.9	1	0.9	0.7	0.2	
B	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.7	0.9	1	0.9	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	
SB	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.5	0.7	0.9	1	0.9	0.7	0.2	0	0	0	0	
RAM	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	0.9	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
M	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	1	0.9	0.9	0.7	0.5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
RBM	0	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.9	0.9	1	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
SS	0	0	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.8	0.9	1	0.9	0.9	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
S	0	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.9	0.9	1	0.8	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
VS	0.5	0.7	0.9	1	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
ES	0.7	1	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.5	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Inference IV (4/4)

Fuzzification

Convert the input real values into "Elements" based on the Universe of Discourse (Table B-4-1).

•**α1**: Select Element **0–25** based on its real value range.

2. Membership Grade Extraction & Safety Exit

Identify the membership grade (μ) for the selected Element using Table B-4-3.

•**CRITICAL EXIT**: If the membership grade μ of the selected input is **LESS THAN 0.7**:

•Set $\Delta Ki = 0$.

•**TERMINATE** the entire inference loop immediately. No further processes or inferences are executed.

•**PROCEED**: If the membership grade μ is **0.7 or higher**, proceed to the Adjustment Rules.

•**Crucial Rule for Output Determination (Aggregation & Defuzzification)**:

If multiple $\alpha 1$ labels (e.g., "B" and "VB") share the same maximum membership grade, the system must not pick only one. Instead, you must follow these exact steps: (1) Independent Evaluation: Identify the target Element Number of ΔKi for each applicable label independently based on the rules. (2) Mean of Indices with Roundup: Calculate the arithmetic mean of all identified Element Numbers. If the result has a decimal, you must round it up (ceil) to the next integer. (3) retrieve the final gain value ΔKi from Table B-4-2 using this unified Element Number. (4)

TERMINATE the entire inference loop immediately. No further processes or inferences are executed

For instance, If Label "B" points to Element 16 and Label "VB" points to Element 20: Calculation: $(16 + 20) / 2 = 18$: The value at Element 18 (which is $\Delta Ki=15$), not Element 16 or 20. Note that "B" and "VB" share the same maximum membership grade in this case.

3. Adjustment Rules (Complete Rule Base)

Apply the following linguistic rules to determine the output label. In Inference III, $\alpha 1$ labels map directly to ΔKi labels.

•**Rule 1**: $\alpha 1$ is EB THEN $\Delta Ki = EB$

•**Rule 2**: ELSE IF $\alpha 1$ is VB THEN $\Delta Ki = VB$

•**Rule 3**: ELSE IF $\alpha 1$ is B THEN $\Delta Ki = B$

•**Rule 4**: ELSE IF $\alpha 1$ is SB THEN $\Delta Ki = SB$

•**Rule 5**: ELSE IF $\alpha 1$ is RAM THEN $\Delta Ki = RAM$

•**Rule 6**: ELSE IF $\alpha 1$ is M THEN $\Delta Ki = M$

•**Rule 7**: ELSE IF $\alpha 1$ is RBM THEN $\Delta Ki = RBM$

•**Rule 8**: ELSE IF $\alpha 1$ is SS THEN $\Delta Ki = SS$

•**Rule 9**: ELSE IF $\alpha 1$ is S THEN $\Delta Ki = S$

•**Rule 10**: ELSE IF $\alpha 1$ is VS THEN $\Delta Ki = VS$

•**Rule 11**: ELSE IF $\alpha 1$ is ES THEN $\Delta Ki = ES$

4. Defuzzification & Loop Termination

4-1. Identify the resulting ΔKi Element based on the selected label and its membership grade from Table B-4-4.

4-2. **Mean of Maxima (MoM)**: If multiple output Elements share the same maximum membership value, use the **Mean of Maxima** method to select the final output Element.

4-3. **Final Conversion**: Map the selected Element to the "Output Value" (0–70) as defined in Table B-4-2.

4-4. **EXIT CONDITION**: If the membership grade μ of the selected output is **LESS THAN 0.7**, set $\Delta Ki = 0$.

4-5. **SYSTEM TERMINATION**: After completing these steps, the entire inference loop ends. There are no subsequent inference stages after Inference IV.

Inference IV: Rule Matrix ($\alpha 1 \rightarrow \Delta Ki$)

$\alpha 1$ (Input)	ΔKi (Output)
EB	EB
VB	VB
B	B
SB	SB
RAM	RAM
M	M
RBM	RBM
SS	SS
S	S
VS	VS
ES	ES

※ Adjustment Rules:

IF $\alpha 1$ is [Label] THEN ΔKi is [Result]

Definition of Area Damping (Decay) Ratios ($\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_5$)

Fig. A-2: Definition of Deviation Areas

Calculation Formulas for Area Damping (Decay) Ratios

.The input variables α_1 through α_5 are defined by the following ratios (expressed as percentages):

$$\alpha_1 = (|A_{-1}| / |A_{+1}|) \times 100 [\%]$$

$$\alpha_2 = (|A_{+2}| / |A_{+1}|) \times 100 [\%]$$

$$\alpha_3 = (|A_{-2}| / |A_{-1}|) \times 100 [\%]$$

$$\alpha_4 = (|A_{+2}| / |A_{-1}|) \times 100 [\%]$$

$$\alpha_5 = (|A_{+3}| / |A_{+1}|) \times 100 [\%]$$